

Centipedes (Chilopoda) from Greece in the collection of the National Museum of Natural History, Sofia

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Abstract. The paper is devoted to the treatment of the centipedes in the National Museum of Natural History, Sofia collected by Bulgarian zoologists in Greece. It deals with material gathered in the provinces of Macedonia and Thrace, and the islands of Tassos, Thasopulo, Samothraki, Kythira, Syros, Amorgos, Santorini, Kalymnos and Karpathos. A total of 22 species were identified, three of them, *Litobius ferganensis* Trotzina, 1880, *L. vizicae* (Ribarov, 1987) and *Hemia* (*Turkophilus*) *porosa* (Verhoeff, 1941), are new to the fauna of the country. An examination of the holotype of *Litobius serresensis* Matic et Stavropoulos, 1990 showed that it is a junior synonym of *Litobius schuleri* Verhoeff, 1925, not of *L. erythrocephalus* C.L. Koch, 1847 as thought previously. *Litobius vizicae* (Ribarov, 1987) is briefly re-described and its taxonomic position discussed.

Key words: Centipedes, Chilopoda, Faunistics, Taxonomy, Greece

Introduction

The Greek centipede fauna is among the richest in species in Europe and is undoubtedly very attractive for biogeographical analysis. Even though it has been an object of intensive investigation almost since the beginning of the nineteenth century, yet very little is known about some regions of mainland Greece and most of the islands. The ecology of certain species and the species communities are also insufficiently known. Many taxa are imprecisely diagnosed or known only from their original description. All the information concerning the taxonomic status, general and country distribution, phenology and ecology of the Greek centipedes was reviewed in detail by ZAPPAROLI (2002).

Among the hundreds of unidentified specimens in the collection of Chilopoda of the National Museum of Natural History in Sofia (NMNHS) a considerable number come from the neighbouring country of Greece. Different generations of Bulgarian zoologists have been collecting invertebrates from the region, most extensively from Macedonia, Thrace, Chalkidiki and the islands Thassos and Samothraki. Since the 1970s Dr. Petar Beron and his colleagues Dr. Vladimir Beshkov, Dr. Stoitse Andreev, Dr. A. Bartsiokas have implemented a broad inventoring campaign, emphasizing the cave and high mountain faunae. This resulted in collecting a large number of soil arthropods, among which also a huge number of myriapods.

A substantial part of this collection has already been studied by MATIC (1980), MATIC & STAVROPOULOS (1988, 1990, 1993) and STAVROPOULOS & MATIC (1990).

In the autumn of 2000, Boyan Petrov, Dr. Stoyan Beshkov and I (all from the NMNHS) carried out a scientific expedition to northern Greece, including the Rhodopi, Olympos, Menikio and Falakro mountains and the Chalkidiki Peninsula. Different soil arthropods were gathered using various sampling methods, but mostly through hand collecting and sifting leaf litter. Special attention was paid to the fauna of the caves in the vicinities of the villages of Zigos, Maronia, Alistrati and Pachni, and along the river of Nestos.

The present work records only a part of the Greek collection in the NMNHS. It deals mostly with materials collected during the trip of Petrov, Stoev and Beshkov and those collected at the beginning of the last century by I. Buresch, N. Stoyanov, N. Karnozhitski, I. Tsonkov, D. Papazov, A. Petrov, V. Petrov and K. Tuleshkov in Thrace, Olympos and Thassos. A total of 22 species were identified, three of them, *Lithobius ferganensis* Trotzina, 1880, *L. vizicae* (Ribarov, 1987) and *Henia (Turkophilus) porosa* (Verhoeff, 1941), appeared to be new to the country's fauna.

Material and methods

Species identification was made with the aid of an MBC-10 stereoscope, made in Russia. All centipedes are preserved in 70% ethanol. The whole collection is preserved in the Department of Non-Insect Invertebrates of the NMNHS. The general distribution is given only for the new species. Species localities are transliterated into English.

List of species

Lithobiomorpha

Eupolybothrus litoralis (L. Koch, 1867)

Material examined: Rhodopi Mts.: subad., village of M. Evmiro, alt. ca. 300 m, oak litter, 26.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; Thassos Is.: 2 ad. ♂♂, 2 ad. ♀♀, near St. Athanasos Monastery above Limena, 26.06.1942, I. Tsonkov leg.; several ♂♂, ♀♀, near Limena, 24.10.1942, collector unknown; ad. ♂, same locality, 24.04.1943, N. Karnozhitski leg.; ad. ♀, Limena, below Prophet Iliya Peak, 27.04.1943, N. Karnozhitski leg.; ad. ♀, Limena - Rahoni, 21.06.1942, I. Tsonkov leg.; ad. ♀, village of Rahoni, Kazaviti Rock, 27.10.1942, collector unknown; ♂, ♀, village of Marios, 08.06.1943, I. Tsonkov leg.; Samothraki Is.: ad. ♀, 25.04.1943, A. Petrov leg.; several ♂♂, ♀♀, 24.05.1988, G. Ribarov leg.; Amorgos Is.: ad. ♂, ad. ♀, Katapola, 13.09.1981, P. Beron, A. Bartsiakos leg.; Syros Is.: ad. ♂, 2 ad. ♀♀, 3 subad., Ano Syros - Mytakas, 30.12.2002, P. Beron leg.

Note. These are the first records of *E. litoralis* for the islands of Samothraki, Amorgos and Syros.

Eupolybothrus transsylvanicus transsylvanicus (Latzel, 1882)

Material examined: Menikio Mts.: ad. ♂, subad. ♂, Timios Prodromous Monastery, 11 km from Seres, Piladele Cave, alt. ca. 500 m, under stones, guano, 19.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; Rhodopi Mts.: ad. ♂, Xanthi District, village of Pachni, a small nameless cave

below Doupkata Cave, alt. ca. 600 m, under stones, 25.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; ad. ♂, Didimoticho District, village of Koufovouno, Koufovouno Cave, under stones, guano, 29.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.

Note. The examined specimens belong to the nominate form characterized by projections on the 6th, 7th, 9th, 11th and 13th tergites.

***Eupolybothrus weneri* (Attems, 1903)**

Material examined: Olympos (Ólimbos) Mts.: ad. ♂, near a cave, alt. ca. 1300 m, 07.07.1936, K. Tuleshkov leg.; ad. ♂, subad. ♀, 10 km above village of Kalivia, alt. ca. 1500 m, under stones, 16.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.

Notes. This species is restricted to the mountains of mainland Greece (Olympos, Parnassos, Vermio, Timfristos, Giona, Erimanthos, Aroania, Killini, Lambia) and the Llogorase Pass in Albania. It occurs in the zone between 700 and 2240 m altitude (ZAPPAROLI, 2002). A morphologically similar species to *weneri*, *E. dolops*, was described from near Stournaraiika and Kataras Pass in Pindos Mts. (ZAPPAROLI, 1998).

***Lithobius* (s. str.) *forficatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined: Falakro Mts.: 2 ad. ♂♂, above the ski-center, alt. ca. 2000 m, 21.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; 2 ad. ♀♀, a pass between the mountains Menikio and Vrontou (Vrontous), alt. ca. 900 m, beech litter, 29.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; Rhodopi Mts.: ad. ♀, 11 km from Leptokaria, alt. ca. 920 m, *Pinetum*, under logs, 27.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.

Note. It is worth mentioning that though very common in other parts of Europe, *L. forficatus* has so far been recorded in Greece only in the Falakro, Vrontou, Menikio and Rhodopi mountains, and the island of Samothraki (ZAPPAROLI, 2002; present study).

***Lithobius* (s. str.) *mutabilis* L. Koch, 1862**

Material examined: Rhodopi Mts.: subad. ♂, ad. ♀, Drama District, between Elatjas Forestry Enterprise and Thermi, alt. ca. 1100 m, broad-leaved forest, leaf litter and under stones, 24.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.

Note. This is the first record of *L. mutabilis* in northeastern Greece (Thráki province).

***Lithobius* (s. str.) *nigripalpis* L. Koch, 1867**

Material examined: ad. ♂, ad. ♀, a pass between the mountains Menikio and Vrontou, alt. ca. 900 m, beech litter, 29.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; Syros Is.: 2 ad. ♂♂, 2 ad. ♀♀, 1 subad., Ano Syros - Mytakas, 30.12.2002, P. Beron leg.

Note. This is the first record of *L. nigripalpis* in Syros Island.

***Lithobius* (*Monotarsobius*) *ferganensis* Trotzina, 1880**

Material examined: Rhodopi Mts.: ad. ♂, 2 subad. ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, 11 km from Leptokaria, alt. ca. 920 m, *Pinetum*, under logs, 27.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.

General distribution. Karakoram, Central Asia, Caucasus, Crimea, Greece.

Notes. This species is widespread in Central Asia, Caucasus and Crimea reaching Chinese Karakoram in the east (EASON, 1997). Until recently, it was known from Turkey as *Monotarsobius curtipes turkestanicus* Attems, 1904 and *Monotarsobius nodonotatus* Verhoeff, 1943, both taxa included

in the list of synonyms of *ferganensis* (EASON, 1997; ZAPPAROLI, 1999). The new record forms the westernmost border of species distribution. It is a new species for the Greek fauna.

***Lithobius (Sigibius) microps* Meinert, 1868**

Material examined: Rhodopi Mts.: 2 ad. ♀♀, Drama District, between Elatjas Forestry Enterprise and Thermi, alt. ca. 1100 m, broad-leaved forest, leaf litter and under stones, 24.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; ad. ♂, 2 ad. ♀♀, Drama District, village of Skaloti, near Elatjas Forestry Enterprise, Chakalos Peak, beech litter, alt. ca. 1800 m, 24.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; ad. ♂, Falakro Mts.: Volakas, alt. ca. 970 m, *Fagetum*, leaf litter and under stones, 20.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; ad. ♂, a pass between the mountains Menikio and Vrondou, alt. ca. 900 m, beech litter, 29.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg. Samothraki Is.: ad. ♀, village of Chora, 200-1000 m, 25.05.1984, P. Beron leg.

***Lithobius (Sigibius) vizicae* (Ribarov, 1987)**

Material examined: Rhodopi Mts.: 2 ad. ♂♂, ad. ♀, village of Dadja, Dadja Monastery, oak forest, dry, under stones, leaf litter, 28.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.

General distribution. Southeastern Bulgaria, Northeastern Greece.

Description: Color: pale brown - yellowish. Head: longer rather than broad; posterior marginal ridge with medial thickening. Antennae: as long as the posterior edge of third tergite; composed of 28-29 articles; ultimate article about 1.2-1.5 times longer than penultimate one. Ocelli: 3, black, in a single row. Tömösváry's organ: equal in size to ocella. Prosternum: with 2+2 broadly separated teeth and very short and stout porodonts, emerging laterally to the lateral teeth. Medial concavity, deep and evenly rounded. Coxal pores: 2, 2, 2, 2; circular, well separated from each other. Tergites: smooth, without posterior projections; 10th and 12th tergites cover 11th and 13th, respectively. Posterior pair of legs: thickened femur and tibia; accessory apical claw present; internal pores are large and cover the whole surface of the legs. Female gonopods: with 2+2 long spurs and bipartite terminal article; lateral tooth emerges at the base of the principle claw as figured by RIBAROV (1987).

Notes. This species was described by RIBAROV (1987) from the Strandzha Mts., southeastern Bulgaria. Its closest relative in the Balkans is *L. trebinjanus* Verhoeff, 1900 from Albania, Montenegro and Bosnia and Herzegovina (re-description in EASON, 1983). Both species can be distinguished from each other by the number of antennal articles (26-29 vs. 42-43 in *trebinjanus*), shape of the terminal claw of the female gonopods (with basal protuberance vs. tripartite, with well-developed medial and smaller lateral denticle) and the shape of the 15th male tibia (hairless vs. distal third densely setose). The only character in common, making them a single group is the form of the prosternum, bearing 2+2 small teeth and very stout porodonts. Another Bulgarian congener having this peculiar character is *L. strandzanicus* (Ribarov, 1987), a species of uncertain taxonomic position. *Lithobius vizicae* is a new species to the fauna of Greece.

A note on the status of *Lithobius seresensis* Matic et Stavropoulos, 1990

L. seresensis Matic et Stavropoulos, 1990 has been described on the basis of a single female specimen collected in the region of Seres (North Greece). ZAPPAROLI (1994) assumed it to be a synonym of *Lithobius erythrocephalus* C.L. Koch, 1847, although he never studied the type. After a re-examination of the holotype kept in the NMNHS, it became clear that this species is based on an aberrant specimen of *Lithobius schuleri* Verhoeff, 1925. Hence, it should be removed from the list of synonyms of *erythrocephalus* and put in that of *schuleri*.

Scolopendromorpha

***Scolopendra cingulata* Latreille, 1829**

Material examined: Thrace (Thráki): subad., Sketscha (Xanthi), 26.04.1914, I. Buresch leg.; 4 subadults, Kavala, 24.04.1942, V. Petrov leg.; 5 specimens, same locality, 18.04.1943, N. Karnozhitski leg.; Thassos Is.: subad., 23.02.1942, N. Stoyanov leg.; subad., October, 1942, collector unknown; 4 specimens, May, 1943, N. Karnozhitski leg.; ad., Limenaria, 28.04.1942, V. Petrov leg.; one specimen, same locality, 01.05.1943, collector unknown; one specimen, same locality, 10.06.1943, I. Tsonkov leg.; 9 adults, 3 juv., Limena, 20-28.04.1943, N. Karnozhitski leg.; one subad., same locality, 24.10.1942, collector unknown; one ad., above Limena, near St. Athanasos Monastery, 24.06.1942, I. Tsonkov leg.; one specimen, village of Marius, 08.06.1943, I. Tsonkov leg.; one adult, one subad., near village of Potamyia, 24.06.1942, I. Tsonkov leg.; 3 adults, 3 juv., village of Rahoni, Kazaviti Rock, 24-27.10.1942, collector unknown; Thasopulo Is.: one juv., 26.06.1942, I. Tsonkov leg.; Samothraki Is.: one adult, one juv., 25.04.1943, A. Petrov leg.; one specimen, 24.05.1988, G. Ribarov leg.; Kalymnos Is.: one subad., village of Skalia, alt. 0-100 m, 04.05.1987, P. Beron leg.

Note. This is the first record of *S. cingulata* in the island of Kalymnos.

***Cryptops anomalans* Newport, 1844**

Material examined: Thassos Is.: 2 adults, October, 1942, collector unknown; 2 adults, one subad., Limena, 02.05.1942, V. Petrov leg.; one ad., same locality, 0-200 m, 24.10.1942, collector unknown; 4 adults, same locality, 20.04-01.05.1943, N. Karnozhitski leg.

Note. These are the first records of *C. anomalans* in Thassos.

***Cryptops croaticus* Verhoeff, 1931**

Material examined: Menikio Mts.: one adult, Seres District, Timios Prodromus Monastery, Lakosh, ruins, near a stream, alt. ca. 500 m, *Platanus* forest, under stones, 20.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.

Notes. The only recent and reliable record of this species in Greece is that of MATIC (1976) from Lefkada (Lefkáda) Isle. The new record verifies its presence in Greece and considerably extends the species range in a northeast direction. This find is not surprising since *C. croaticus* has already been reported from the Bulgarian part of the Slavyanka (Orvilos) Mts. (STOEV, 2002), which is situated close to Menikio.

***Cryptops hortensis* (Donovan, 1810)**

Material examined: Rhodopi Mts.: several specimens, Drama District, between Elatjas Forestry Enterprise and Thermi, alt. ca. 1100 m, broad-leaved forest, leaf litter and under stones, 24.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; several specimens, a pass between the mountains Menikio and Vrontou, alt. ca. 900 m, beech litter, 29.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; 1 specimen, Alexandroupoli District, Leptokaria, beech litter, alt. ca. 740 m, 27.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; Thassos Is.: one specimen, Kazaviti Rock, 28.10.1942, collector unknown.

***Cryptops parisi* Brolemann, 1920**

Material examined: Falakro Mts.: one specimen, Volakas, alt. ca. 970 m, *Fagetum*, leaf litter and under stones, 20.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; several specimens, a pass between the mountains Menikio and Vrontou, alt. ca. 900 m, beech litter, 20.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; Rhodopi Mts.: 2 specimens, Xanthi District, village of Pachni, alt. ca. 600 m,

beech litter, 25.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; one specimen, Alexandroupoli District, Leptokaria, beech litter, alt. ca. 740 m, 27.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; Santorini (= Thira) Is.: 5 specimens, under stones, 03.10.1974, P. Beron, V. Beshkov leg.

Notes. Until now *C. parisi* has been known only from the mainland part of Greece and the Ionian Islands (ZAPPAROLI, 2002). The new record from Santorini Island extends its range in a southeast direction, including the Aegean Islands.

Geophilomorpha

***Clinopodes flavidus* C.L. Koch, 1847**

Material examined: 2 ad. ♀♀, Alexandroupoli District, village of Essimi, 18.05.1981, P. Beron leg.; Thassos Is.: one ad. specimen, Acropolis above Limena, 25.06.1942, I. Tsonkov leg.; ad. ♂, ad. ♀, Limena, 24.04.1943, N. Karnozhitski leg.; Thasopulo Is.: ad. ♀, 01.05.1942, V. Petrov leg.; Samothraki Is.: ad. ♂, 24.05.1988, G. Ribarov leg.

***Pachymerium ferrugineum* (C.L. Koch, 1835)**

Material examined: Lekani Mts.: ♀, Kavala District, village of Drimia, *Quercetum*, alt. ca. 200 m, leaf litter and under stones, 25.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; Thassos Is.: several specimens, Kazaviti Rock, 28.10.1942, collector unknown; Kythira Is.: ad. ♀ with 59 pairs of legs, village of Mylopotamos, 28.04.1987, P. Beron leg.; Santorini Is.: 4 ads., one of which with 61 pairs of legs, village of Akrotiri, 05.10.1974, P. Beron, V. Beshkov leg.; Syros Is.: one ad., one subad., Ano Syros - Mytakas, 30.12.2002, P. Beron leg.

Note. These are the first records of *P. ferrugineum* from the islands Thassos and Kythira.

***Dignathodon microcephalus* (Lucas, 1846)**

Material examined: Lekani Mts.: ♂, Kavala District, village of Drimia, *Quercetum*, alt. ca. 200 m, leaf litter and under stones, 25.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.

Note. This is the first record of *D. microcephalus* in the province of Macedonia.

***Henia illyrica* (Meinert, 1870)**

Material examined: Chalkidiki Peninsula: one subad. ♂ with 85 pairs of legs, Athon, 27.06.1936, D. Papazov leg.; Drama Distr.: ad. ♂, ad. ♀, Prossotsani Region, village of Angitis, under stones, 28.09.2002, P. Beron leg.; Thrace: ad. ♂, Kavala, 24.04.1942, V. Petrov leg.; Rhodopi Mts.: 2 ad. ♀♀, Xanthi District, village of Pachni, alt. ca. 600 m, beech litter, 25.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; Thassos Is.: one ad. ♀, Acropolis above Limena, 25.06.1942, I. Tsonkov leg.; ad. ♂ with 85 pairs of legs, ad. ♀ with 91 pairs of legs, near Limena, 24.10.1942, collector unknown.

Note. These are the first records of *H. illyrica* in the Rhodopi Mts., Chalkidiki Peninsula and Thassos Island.

***Henia (Turkophilus) porosa* (Verhoeff, 1941)**

Material examined: Rhodopi Mts., ad. ♀, village of Dadja, Dadja Monastery, oak forest, dry, under stones, leaf litter, 28.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.

General distribution. Northwest Turkey, Southeast Bulgaria, Northeast Greece.

Notes. *Henia porosa* is widespread in southeast Bulgaria (sub *H. angelovi* Ribarov, 1987) and the regions of Marmara and West Pontus in Turkey (ZAPPAROLI, 1999). It is the first record from Greece.

***Strigamia transilvanica* (Verhoeff, 1928)**

Material examined: Rhodopi Mts.: ♂ with 47 pairs of legs, Drama District, between Elatjas Forestry Enterprise and Thermi, alt. ca. 1100 m, broad-leaved forest, leaf litter and under stones, 24.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.

***Himantarium gabrielis* (Linnaeus, 1767)**

Material examined: Thrace: several specimens, Kavala, 18.04.1943, N. Karnozhitski leg.; Thassos Is.: ad. ♀, Limena, 02.05.1942, V. Petrov leg.; 3 ad. ♀♀, same locality, 24-27.04.1943, N. Karnozhitski leg.; 2 ad. ♀♀, Limena, below Prophet Iliya Peak, *Pinetum*, 26.04.1943, N. Karnozhitski leg.; Karpathos Is.: ad. ♀, Arch. Michail, alt. 800-1000 m, 04.05.1984, P. Beron leg.

Note. These are the first records of *H. gabrielis* from the islands of Thassos and Karpathos.

***Bothriogaster signata* (Kessler, 1874)**

Material examined: Thrace: 3 specimens, Kavala, 24.04.1942, V. Petrov leg.; one specimen, same locality, 18.04.1943, N. Karnozhitski leg.; ♂, Komotini District, 10 km E of village of Maronia, alt. ca. 100 m, *Olea europaea* forest mixed with *Quercus coccifera*, 27.09.2000, Petrov, Stoev, Beshkov leg.; Samothraki Is.: 3 specimens, 25.04.1943, A. Petrov leg.; Karpathos Is.: one specimen, village of Karpathos (Pighadia), 02.05.1984, P. Beron leg.; Santorini Is.: ad. ♂, “*Stigmatogaster gracilis* Z. Matic det.”, 05.10.1974, P. Beron, V. Beshkov leg.

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**Хилоподи (Chilopoda) от Гърция в колекцията на
Националния природонаучен музей, София**

Павел СТОЕВ

(Резюме)

Съобщават се 22 вида хилоподи от колекцията на Националния природонаучен музей в София, събрани в Северна Гърция (Македония, Тракия) и островите Тасос, Тасопуло, Самотраки, Китура, Сирос, Аморгос, Санторин, Калинос, и Карпатос. *Lithobius ferganensis* Trotzina, 1880, *L. vizicae* (Ribarov, 1987) и *Henia (Turkophilus) porosa* (Verhoeff, 1941) са нови за фауната на Гърция. Нови за фауната на Тасос са *Cryptops anomalans*, *Pachymerium ferrugineum*, *Henia illyrica* и *Himantarium gabrielis*; за Самотраки и Аморгос – *Eupolybothrus litoralis*; за Китура – *P. ferrugineum*; за Сирос – *E. litoralis* и *Lithobius nigripalpis*; за Санторин – *Cryptops parisi*; за Калинос – *Scolopendra cingulata*; за Карпатос – *H. gabrielis*; за провинция Тракия – *Lithobius mutabilis*; за провинция Македония – *Cryptops croaticus* и *Dignathodon microcephalus*. След преразглеждане на холоטיפа, *Lithobius seresensis* Matic et Stavropoulos, 1990 е обявен за синоним на *Lithobius schuleri* Verhoeff, 1925, а не както се смяташе госега на *L. erythrocephalus* C.L. Koch, 1847. *Lithobius vizicae* е преописан по материали от района на манастира Дада в Североизточна Гърция.